

SSHOC

social sciences & humanities open cloud

Supplementary Guide for Trainers for the Canonical Training Materials

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Supplementary Guide for Trainers for the Canonical Training Materials

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Abstract: This document is part of the SSHOC deliverable D5.20 Training materials of workshop for secure data facility professionals and is created to aid development and delivery of courses for data facility professionals.

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1 The purpose of these training materials

Where access to secure data is provided via a physical safe data enclave or safe room physical controls, such as not allowing researchers to take electron devices into the room, are in place to ensure that data can be used safely in a way that reduces the risk of re-identification of data subjects. Where access to secure data is provided via a virtual data enclave (remote access, remote desktop, etc.) fewer physical controls can be put in place, so additional safeguards are required. These safeguards take a number of forms – licenses, data use agreements and contracts, but also often include mandatory training for researchers as part of the application process. This training can cover a range of different topics depending on the specific requirements of the secure data service but will typically include information on the legislative frameworks or constraints, service specific information and statistical disclosure. The aim of such training is to ensure that researchers are equipped with the knowledge required to use secure data safely.

For any service looking to develop a safe researcher type training course, developing the training materials can be resource intensive if you are required to start from scratch. The aim of these training materials is to provide secure data access services with a canonical set of materials that they can adapt to meet the specific needs of their service. In this way reducing the overall burden of developing a safe researcher training course.

2 Guidance on adapting the slides for your service

2.1 Understanding your audience

One of the key things to consider when adapting these materials to develop a safe researcher training course, is a careful assessment of your target audience. Some content may be more relevant to some audiences than others. Some important things to consider are:

- The level of prior knowledge or experience of data protection.
- The level of statistical knowledge or experience.
- What sector are your audience from? E.g., academia or civil service?
- What academic discipline are your audience from (certain disciplines will favour certain types of output for example)?

Having a clear understanding of the target audience will help with deciding what content to include, and what content can be excluded. For example, if the audience is primarily data access professionals, then the content in module 2 could be reduced accordingly. Likewise with a clear understanding of the discipline of an academic audience, certain output types not commonly produced could be removed from module 5.

2.2 Deciding on the delivery mode

These materials are designed as a taught course that could work equally for in-person delivery or online delivery. In this guide you will find a slide-by-slide guide with notes to aid delivery. These are not intended to be a verbatim script but should guide trainers to the content and its purpose.

There are benefits to both delivery modes. Delivering training in-person allows trainers to build up a good relationship with the researchers who they will be supporting. This can be particularly useful when it is necessary to discuss potential problems with outputs for example. However, in-person training is time and cost intensive, as trainers often need to travel to locations. This is also true for researchers, who may have to travel some distance to attend training sessions.

During the recent pandemic, training has shifted to virtual delivery with great success and researchers have been appreciative of not having to travel. The cautionary note with virtual delivery is to think carefully about the length of the course. Experience shows that courses often need to be shorter, so you may want to consider moving some course content into a supplementary handout. You will find guidance in the delivery notes to indicate which content could be provided in this way.

Currently the content is arranged into 6 modules to ensure that each section covers a distinct topic giving a clear structure for trainers and participants a clear structure to follow. The other benefit of arranging the content in this way, is that it would allow the content to be adapted more easily to an online, self-study format, should that be preferred delivery mode. This may be an attractive option for services that do not have the resources to run training events regularly.

For those seeking to develop an online self-study course, the core content can still be used as the basis for the course. You might want to consider the following adaptations to the materials in order to successfully convert the materials for self-study. For example, more information would need to be added to the slides, but this can be taken from the delivery note. You may also want to consider delivering some of the material as short video recordings to avoid simply reading through slides on screen.

2.2.1 Delivery notes

In the Table 1 below, are delivery notes which are designed to aid trainers in the delivery of the content. For some slides, the notes will just indicate the purpose of the slides, for others the notes will explain the content in more detail, especially where the slide includes technical information or examples. Where the slide is just a title slide or outline slide, no delivery notes are included.

These delivery notes are not designed to be a verbatim script, but rather they are a guide to the key messages that need to be discussed. This approach allows the materials to accommodate individual trainers' delivery style and the priorities of each data service.

Table 1: Overview of slides and delivery notes

Slide 1	Title page
Slide 2	Overview of course

Slide 3	Module 1 title page
Slide 4	Module 1 outline
Slide 5	<p>This slide introduces the benefits of making secure data available for research. The follow example text could be used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Society is ever changing, and we can argue that it's becoming more complex. Not only do we need to understand what society looks like, we need to understand how it functions and how it changes. • For example, of course economists are interested in understanding at the macrolevel how the economy is performing, but at the microlevel, they might want to understand how a household reacts to an economic shock such as unemployment. • Local government agencies need to measure the local population trends so they can plan for future health and education services. But we might also be interested in identifying inequalities, to understand which groups suffer poorer outcomes and what factors may lead to those groups being more vulnerable. • Making secure microdata available enables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers want to access much more detailed information – essential for many research areas. • Vital research that informs evidence-based policies. • The level of detail enables us to link survey and admin data together to get new insights which have been previously impossible & which wouldn't be possible without these data. • Maximum use of publicly funded data collections by encouraging secondary analysis etc.
Slide 6	<p>This slide aims to introduce the idea that as we make more data available, we need to think about what impact that has. A particular point to highlight is that more access means we have to consider how to safeguard the data!</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All of that means that we are seeing an increased demand for very detailed microdata. • As more detailed data becomes available, the scope and detail of research that is possible also expands....and so do the expectations of researchers! • Some microdata can be successfully anonymised without losing too much utility but not all. • So, in order to make very detailed, potentially disclosive data available for research, we need to look at appropriate safeguarding of the data.
Slide 7	<p>This slide looks at some of the reasons why we need to safeguard data. Key points to highlight are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • That increased data equals increased risk of re-identification. • Discuss the concerns & highlight that these are valid concerns. • All data access solutions must address these concerns.

	<p>This final point is important as it is the first key principle that underlines all following content on understanding data access.</p>
Slide 8	<p>This slide highlights the bottom line that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Whilst data security is a collective responsibility, one person committing a breach or behaving irresponsibly, everyone loses. EMPHASISE THIS POINT! • It is important to remember that data from social surveys, administrative data, etc. comes from members of the public – who entrust us with the very intimate details of their lives. • Public often don't know about secure research environments but they do see media reports of breaches and they don't distinguish between breaches that stem from things that are unforeseeable and those that come from incompetence or malicious behaviour. • Breaches erode the public's trust in the statistical bodies handling their data. • So, the key to gaining and keeping access is to demonstrate that we can be trusted to look after their data. • We must do this consistently! • The good news is that there is generally wide support for academic use of their data and researchers have a good track record – they demonstrate that they respect the privilege of data access. • It should be made clear at the start of the course that the course will focus on quantitative data throughout.
Slide 9	<p>Module summary - emphasise that this is common sense!</p>
Slide 10	<p>Module 2 title page</p>
Slide 11	<p>Module 2 outline</p>
Slide 12	<p>This slide offers a definition of secure data - where it comes from & what it might include (this can be adjusted to suit your own service).</p> <p>If you are in a country subject to the GDPR, point out that secure data is considered 'personal data' under the GDPR.</p>
Slide 13	<p>This slide continues with some key definitions regarding anonymisation. Researchers are often not clear on these separate categories and believe that secure is anonymised - highlight that this is not the case. Secure data is pseudonymised (important as underpins why we safeguard the data (modules 3-4) & do statistical disclosure control (module 5).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifiable data: source data or raw data. All the data collected is included, such as name. • Pseudonymised data: Includes most of the data; some techniques have been applied to protect confidentiality i.e., direct identifiers removed.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • But we could still potentially identify individuals because there is sufficiently detailed information to allow for jigsaw identification (piecing together the information to build a detailed picture of an individual). • Anonymisation techniques have been applied which means there should be only a negligible risk to identifying someone in the data.
Slide 14	<p>This is the data access spectrum.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explain the different types of data if appropriate for your audience. • Explain that the 'residual risk' is the remaining risk of re-identification. • Risk of re-identification and association with confidential data is high with source data and decreases as we move towards open data. • The techniques that turn source data into Secure, SUF, PUF and Web all act to make the data more and more anonymous.
Slide 15	<p>This extends the previous slide by including some legal information to the spectrum:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We can now see how the law applies. Generally, researchers are not allowed access to personally identifiable data. • Where data are pseudonymised through removing direct identifiers but leaving all the remaining data about individuals untouched, there is a real risk that somebody could be identified or have information associated with them. • They will be 'personal' data and the GDPR applies; there should be a legal basis for using the data, safeguards will apply, particularly special categories of data (Article 9). • If greater anonymisation techniques have been applied to the data, then they won't be personal data, and therefore the GDPR may not apply. • But there may still be contractual obligations that you will need to agree to. • Anonymised aggregate data are not personal data at all, so the law doesn't apply, and safeguards are not required. • So now we know about our data types, where they sit on the data access spectrum, and how the law applies to their use. <p>The content can be adjusted if you are in a country where the GDPR doesn't apply to include information on your own data protection legislation. If you do not intend to discuss legislation, then this slide can be removed.</p>
Slide 16	<p>This slide focuses on why we (i.e., a data owner/producer) might decide to restrict access to their data.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal restrictions - determines who can share data with whom and for what purpose. • Perceived risk - different data owners have different levels of experience in data sharing & some are more risk adverse than others. • Incentives to share - may have few incentives to share data (& take the perceived risk), for data collectors, data sharing = more funding, but not for all. • Concern about data intruders - i.e., about people attempting to access data without permission, to identify people, for malicious or criminal intentions.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This is important to consider as it can inform who data access systems are set up – I will explain how that might work now...
Slide 17	<p>The key point here is that if data owners/producers believe that people might have the deliberate intention to breach data confidentiality, they will be reluctant to share their data and data access solutions will be designed to prevent that ‘worst case scenario’. This means that researchers will face greater restrictions when trying to access data.</p>
Slide 18	<p>The Human Model:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Based on the premise that people are human & may make mistakes but not intentional breaches. If the system is well designed and your researchers are trained well, we can allow greater data access. Allows the research community to demonstrate that they can use data safely BEFORE consider tighter restrictions. Accidental intruder – In the intruder model, an intruder will combine data to increase their knowledge and the chance of identification – you could do this accidentally...so if something is not allowed in your research agreement, don’t do it! This is an important point as it reinforces why it is important for researchers to obey the procedural rules of the data access service!
Slide 19	Module 2 summary
Slide 20	Module 3 Title page
Slide 21	<p>Module 3 outline</p> <p>Important note for this module: Consider whether you wish to include information about legislation in your training course!</p> <p>This module can be skipped entirely, or else the information can be moved into a supplementary handout (downloadable PDF if training is online).</p> <p>The benefits of including some general information of the legislation are that it underpins the importance of the procedural rules that secure data access facilities have in place. If your target audience is likely to be less compliant in terms of following rules, it can be helpful for them to understand why these rules are in place. Some researchers will also find the information interesting and is useful general knowledge for all researchers or data access professionals that work with secure data.</p> <p>But it is important to acknowledge that the trainers are not legal experts and therefore the information will be fairly general.</p>
Slide 22	<p>This slide shows an overview of the different types of legislation that might be relevant. It is specific to the EU, so may need replacing or removing if you are outside the EU. This would be highly suitable for a separate handout.</p>

<p>Slide 23</p>	<p>This slide introduces some of the key legislative acts and concepts that are relevant in our discussion of secure data access.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The recommendation here is that details of any country specific legislation is included here. Legislative Acts should take priority here, if there is also space & it's relevant to your context – the concepts of confidentiality can be useful. • This slide can be moved to a supplementary handout instead of discussing it during the course. • Implied consent – for example, if we give information to a doctor, we would expect that this information is shared within the health system. We do not need to give specific consent for this to happen, it is an assumption of what will happen. • Duty of Confidentiality – e.g., we would expect that information we give to our doctors is kept confidential. Whilst we may expect them to share with colleagues, we would not expect them to share our information with their neighbours.
<p>Slide 24</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Details of data protection legislation can be easily found and accessed, but they are very long, complex documents. • Luckily we don't need to be legal experts – but we do need to understand the impact that legislation has on data access and our responsibilities as researchers accessing detailed, confidential data. • The gateways are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Person-specific – if a new researcher wants to join the project, they must seek approval. ▪ Project-specific – The data can only be used for the approved project. If researchers want to use the data for any other purpose they need to apply for a separate project. ▪ Time-specific – Approval is granted for a specific time period only, although researchers can apply for an extension. ▪ Dataset specific – can only access the datasets for which you have been approved. <p>The main point to emphasis is that legislation provides legal gateways that allow access to personal data for research.</p>
<p>Slide 25</p>	<p>This slide summarises some of the key points (if you don't want to include the more detailed information, this slide should ideally remain as an overview. It is vital that researchers understand these points).</p> <p>Key points are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Different data producers may be subject to different legislation. ▪ This may impact what data can be made available & what projects are feasible. ▪ Procedures of data access facilities are determined by the legislation. ▪ They are designed to keep researchers on the right side of this legislation.

Slide 26	<p>Again, this slide summarises some of the key points (if you don't want to include the more detailed information, this slide should ideally remain as an overview. It is vital that researchers understand these points).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If an individual's identity is disclosed – this is breaking the law. • This is important to emphasise! This includes disclosure that results from our use of the data for research purposes! • The data holders/secure data facilities will have procedures in place that specify how you access and use the data. • These must be abided by! • Sticking to these, will help you to ensure you stay on the right side of the law – without needing a law degree. • Breaching the rules of a data access facility is a breach of procedure but may also result in a breach of the law if something goes wrong. • May to be subject to civil penalties (loss of funding, access reputation etc.). • May also lead to legal sanctions.
Slide 27	<p>GROUP EXERCISE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Works either as a small group discussion exercise with feedback to the wider group OR a whole group discussion, depending on size of group, mode of delivery, etc. • Explanation to the group: • Let's look at a practical example of a breach. We have a busy researcher who is in a rush to get a paper finished for an upcoming conference. They are using data about children who are in the care system (i.e., In children's home, foster care, on the at-risk register). • Enough though the secure data environment states that they shouldn't do so, they write down some data on a bit of paper. • In your groups, I want you to think first about what type of breach this is – is it a procedural breach or a legal breach. • Then I want you to think about what the consequences might be as a result of this breach. <p>The aim of the exercise is two-fold:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To discuss whether this is a procedural breach or a legal breach & how one can easily become the other. • Answer: This example begins as a procedural breach but could easily develop into a legal breach. • To think about the consequences – i.e., what sanctions could be handed out. BUT also, to think beyond just the legal aspects, and think about the human consequences of breaches – i.e., given the detailed geographies, reidentification could result from this and if the child is in care due to familial abuse, could result in physical harm. • Important points of discussion: • SANCTIONS: Talk about the possible sanctions (relevant to your service).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some examples might be: • A breach of procedure such as this would result in everyone on the project team getting suspended whilst an investigation is carried out. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The severity of the breach may determine the sanctions. ▪ A breach such as this could result in an indefinite ban from the data access service, or re-training. ▪ Might also be loss of funding, reputation. ▪ Potentially criminal proceedings if leads to disclosure/legal breach. • WIDER IMPLICATIONS: Always consider your actions and their wider implications. For example, if these notes were lost, they could... <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Be picked up by a journalist – bad press, loss of trust in the survey, response rates drop. ▪ A victim of a crime, or a perpetrator could be identified - This would likely cause extreme distress to respondents (even potentially place them in danger). ▪ Data providers would lose trust in the system and be less likely to make their data available. ▪ Reputations of secure data access facilities, in general, would be jeopardised. <p>Encourage your audience to remember that people underlie the data, so they think beyond the numbers!!</p>
Slide 28	<p>This slide shows an example of what an output from this exercise might look like. Here we use a free interactive whiteboard JamBoard. This allows participants to add virtual post-it notes to a board that can be seen and accessed by all in the group.</p>
Slide 29	<p>Model 3 Summary</p>
Slide 30	<p>Module 4 Title page</p>
Slide 31	<p>Module 4 outline</p>
Slide 32	<p>This module introduces the 5 Safes Framework which is widely used globally as a way of thinking about and managing access to secure data.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Five Safes is a way of thinking about managing data access. It was originally devised by Professor Felix Ritchie around 2006). • The framework provides a decision-making process to enable ‘safe use’ of secure data. The framework was drawn up with statistical purposes in mind.
Slide 33	<p>The 5 Safes combined add up to the Safe Use of data – it is crucial to remember however that secure data is often not safe.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When the data isn’t safe, we have to make sure all other aspects of the framework are safe.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The Five Safes is an increasingly common framework for thinking about how to manage data access. ● It breaks down into five principles. ● You need to consider them all together to get an overall 'safe' solution – balancing physical controls (safe setting) with user training (safe people) as we move from access through a SAFE ROOM to a REMOTE ACCESS pathway, for example. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ E.g., we balance the non-statistical controls (projects, people, setting) against the level of data detail, and then add safe outputs to mop up any residual risk.
Slide 34	<p>The next 3 slides discuss the different parts of the 5 Safes Framework in more detail. These can be discussed during the course or could be moved into a supplementary handout if preferred.</p> <p>Safe projects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Requirements for determining a “safe project” will vary – but these are some possible requirements... ● Valid statistical purpose. ● For example, using data to work out who is most likely to suffer poorer outcomes after a cancer diagnosis or how families respond to financial shocks such as unemployment. ● Wanting to identify someone is not a valid purpose. ● There should be a 'public benefit' to the research; and the data must be essential to achieving that benefit. ● Most universities now will insist on an ethical review of any project & some secure access systems will also require an ethics review to be submitted as part of the application. <p>Safe Setting:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Confidential data should only be accessed in an environment that has appropriate safeguards in place. ● Increasing number of ways to access confidential data – <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Safe room ▪ Remote access ▪ Remote desktop ▪ Remote execution <p>Each has different safeguards in place, but all work to minimise the risk that unauthorised people can access the data (i.e., intentional, or unintentional data intrusion!).</p>
Slide 35	<p>Note: Even if you choose to move these slides into a separate handout, I recommend keeping a discussion about safe people in the main presentation!</p>

	<p>Safe people</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safe people are a central part of any data security system and it's really important that researchers know that. • When we move from the greater physical controls of a Safe Room to a remote desktop access, this becomes more pertinent as the reduction in physical controls needs to be balanced by adherence to safe data handling procedures by researchers. • That's something to think about when you're deciding whether to move content out into a supplementary document. • Therefore, this training has been developed (and why many secure data services train their researchers) – working remotely means researchers using secure data can't be constantly monitored, so they need to check themselves and the role of this training is to ensure that researchers have the knowledge to do so effectively. • Some secure access systems will insist on researchers having a certain amount of experience (i.e., length of research experience or qualification level). <p>Safe Data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A safe dataset will present the minimal risk possible that any of the data subjects could be identified. • The minimisation of risk could be achieved by removing direct identifiers, top-coding or banding values or other statistical techniques that make re-identification more difficult but reduces the utility of the data. • Secure data is personal data and not considered to be safe. • Can think of safe data as having an appropriate level of detail for the setting.
Slide 36	<p>Safe outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outputs are the results of analysis that are intended for publication or presentation. • Outputs can be released if they report statistical findings but do not reveal the identity of or associate confidential information to a data subject. • Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC) is often used to minimise this risk of re-identification. • Researchers and/or the secure data centre can check outputs (apply SDC) before publication. • SDC is the focus of the next module (module 5).
Slide 37	<p>Slides 37 & 38 both contain a visual representation of how the 5 Safes works: The recommendation is that you include one of the slides, rather than both depending on the needs of your audience. Slide 37 just looks at secure use files, slide 38 includes secure use files, scientific use files and public us files.</p> <p>The slides both contain animations - as you click through, the equaliser moves to demonstrate how the 5 Safes works.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When data is safe, it doesn't matter if the other 'safes' are not met. Because the data is safe, 'safe use' is achieved without the other aspects being safe. • However, confidential data is unsafe. • Even with names and direct IDs removed, the level of detail is such that it is possible to re-identify people. • Therefore, if we have unsafe data, and any of the other aspects are also unsafe, then we would not have safe use. • When the data is unsafe, but we have safe people, safe projects, safe settings, and safe outputs, we can still have safe use. <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Five Safes should be seen as scales. • The data provider can adjust the degree of control until we get a solution that works for everyone. • Typically, we balance the non-statistical controls (projects, people, setting) against data detail, and then add safe outputs to mop up any residual risk.
Slide 38	<p>As with slide 37, click through the animations to discuss how the 5 Safes would work in each case:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public Use File – No other safeguards needed. If the data is safe there shouldn't be any way to misuse the data. • Scientific Use File – Some residual risk in the data. It will have more detail than a public use file and it might be possible to re-identify someone, but the risk will be minimal. • Safeguards might include having to register to access the data, have the proposed usage approved by the data owner, and storing the data in a restricted area. • Secure Data Environment – (see above slide notes for information).
Slide 39	<p>Module 5 Title page</p> <p>Module 5 is the largest of the modules - for this reason it is split into subsections, each focused on a particular type of output. This structure allows the module to be easily tailored to your specific audience and the type of outputs that you typically see.</p> <p>A wide range of different types of output have been included here, not all of them may be relevant to your audience. So non-relevant examples can be removed without impacting on the remainder of the module sections.</p>
Slide 40	<p>Introduction to safe outputs - why we do SDC</p> <p>The aim of making outputs safe is to reduce the likelihood of an individual being identified, or associating an attribute with someone, from a piece of analysis.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Where we are using potentially identifiable data, SDC needs to be applied to results. • It's important to note that no system is 100% effective, we can never say 100% that an output is 'safe'. • The unprovability of safety – exists because we can never know every single other piece of information or table that is available or may be available in the future. What we're really saying is that we think this output is reasonably safe given the way we have managed low values and other information that is likely to be produced from this data. • The aim is not to pour endless resources that we most likely don't have into checking to ensure that there is no chance of re-identification, but to make it difficult for a reasonably well-equipped data misuser to breach the confidentiality. • There are a number of great resources out there that are freely available which discuss statistical disclosure control – good to point your researchers to some of these.
Slide 41	<p>GROUP EXERCISE: Why should we ensure our research outputs are safe?</p> <p>Similarly, to the previous exercise, divide your audience into small groups and ask them to write down as many reasons as they can think of. For virtual delivery you can use something like JamBoard; give them around 5 mins to discuss.</p> <p>They should be able to draw on the information covered in the previous modules here!</p> <p>Come back as a larger group and talk through what they're listed. Are there any points they missed – some examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal penalties. • Reputational damage to researchers, the survey, the secure data center, etc... • Incur sanctions. • risk of identifying people - potential harm to them. • Loss of confidence in data collection, fewer people taking part.
Slide 42	<p>The key message of this slide is that statistical disclosure control is consistent with good research practices.</p> <p>It is a common misconception among researchers new to SDC that SDC will restrict what they can do. Actually, this is rarely the case so it's good to emphasise this before you start talking about SDC in detail.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In general, the sorts of things that produce good research output also protects against disclosure risk. • E.g., low numbers increase confidentiality risk, but also don't have much statistical value; and the type of analyses that researchers typically are interested in have very low disclosure risk.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Remember, SDC applies at the point at which statistical results are going to be released – not when you’re working with the data.
Slide 43	<p>This slide introduces the theoretical underpinning of SDC & the theoretical threshold of 3. It explains how disclosure can occur using a very simple example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Suppose we collect some confidential information about income. The average income for observations in the data is €43,000, But there are only two observations, including myself. I know my income (€31,000). Therefore, I can easily calculate that the other person’s income is €55,000. So now I have learned confidential information about this person Would this still be the case if there were three observations? No! When there are three or more people in the box, we can’t say with certainty what anyone else earns (assuming no collusion). So, 3 is often referred to as the theoretical ‘safe’ threshold. <p>Whilst this is widely accepted as a theoretical ‘safe’ threshold, in practice different thresholds may be used & we’ll discuss that in more detail in a few minutes (slide 46).</p>
Slide 44	<p>This slide focuses on the two types of disclosure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Primary disclosure - occurs using a single source of information/output. Spontaneous recognition - a researcher believes they have identified someone in the data, not because they are looking for them, but because the level of detail is such that it is possible to do so. They should stop working with the data and contact the secure data centre. It may be that the observation needs to be removed. If they continue to work with the data, it will be considered an attempt to deliberately identify patients and therefore will likely be in breach of the legislation. Secondary disclosure - occurs when two or more pieces of information are combined to identify or attribute information to someone. This is actually a common problem in SDC, and we’ll look at some examples later on of how this might work (& how to avoid it!). This type of disclosure is sometimes referred to as ‘jigsaw identification’ as we put together pieces to build a picture.
Slide 45	<p>This slide is optional and can be removed without detriment to the course if it is not appropriate for your service.</p> <p>It can be useful to promote the benefits of one model over the other if that’s useful for your audience.</p> <p>Rules-based:</p> <p>Users are given a set of rules about what outputs can or cannot be released, if the statistical output presented by the user abides by these rules it can be released.</p>

	<p>Principles-based:</p> <p>An output is assessed, and a decision is made as to whether the output is safe to release or not?</p> <p>There are benefits and limitations of these approaches:</p> <p>Rules model:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● seems easiest: mechanistic, unambiguous, automatic. ● In practice, this is very difficult to apply strictly in a research environment (apart from fully automated job processing systems). ● Why? Because you can't specify all the cases that a genuine research environment will throw up. ● If you have a 'no exceptions' rule, then researchers might be justified in complaining about unnecessary restrictions. ● In practice an output might not meet the criteria for the rules, but actually present no real risk. <p>Principles model:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● As for the rules-based system, we start by defining some rules, but we will call them rules of thumb because we are going to be flexible about how we implement them. ● We then allow everyone to make the case for ignoring the rule of thumb in specific cases, for example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ the support team might argue that class disclosure means you can't have a table however many observations you have. ▪ a researcher might argue that a maximum value should be allowed in a specific case because (a) it is informative about the data but (b) can't be informative about any individual respondent. ● Having these discussions is a valid part of the researcher-support team communication. ● BUT! This is time consuming so we should emphasise these discussions to be rare – use the flexibility when it's important, not as an everyday request.
<p>Slide 46</p>	<p>Research data centres that apply SDC to outputs will stipulate a threshold. This slide gives you the opportunity to inform researchers of your own threshold.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Thresholds vary – some like Statistiks Danmark have a threshold of 3, others will have a higher threshold – for example the CBS Statistics (Netherlands) and the UK Data Service both have a threshold of 10. The highest threshold that I'm aware of is the HMRC (Her Majesty's Revenue & Customs) in the UK which has a threshold of 30. ● Note: Discuss here what your threshold is <p>Thresholds allow; emphasise here that using a threshold allows outputs to be checked in an efficient, timely manner, and reduces the risk of reidentification. It also allows the</p>

	public to have confidence in researchers to use their data safely (small counts don't look safe to the public!).
Slide 47	Module 5.1 Title page
Slide 48	<p>This module looks at frequency tables and some of the key ideas.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequencies can be presented in many ways. • Even if these are presented as graphs all unweighted counts should be made available. Weighted counts may hide counts which are below the required threshold. • Units – Checkers should consider if units have been aggregated up, if there has been any sampling, and the sensitivity of the data being displayed. • The context of the output is also considered when deciding if an output is safe.
Slide 49	<p>This is a simple example of a frequency table - mention here that all output examples that follow are made up and do use genuine data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss what is good about this table? What might cause a concern? • Positives – the categories are clear; output checkers will be able to clearly understand the table and make a judgement as to whether it can be released. • The bad – there is a single male widower in Berlin shown in the data. There are unlikely to be many 16-year-old widowers. As it is so uncommon, if you know a 16-year-old widower in Berlin, it is likely to be the same person. You will now know that they have been diagnosed with NHL which may not be something they want to widely known.
Slide 50	<p>Slides 50-52 discuss different ways that researchers could edit the output to make it safer.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are a number of approaches we can take... such as collapsing categories. • Here we have combined the 'Divorced' and 'Widowed' rows. This has made the output safer.
Slide 51	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We can apply cell suppression. • We could remove the 'Widowed' row from the table altogether or suppress the cells (suppression is the technique whereby the value is removed, and a placeholder left). An example might be to fill both cells with – or '<10' or similar.
Slide 52	<p>Cell suppression will often work but not always. We have to take care with what other information is provided.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Let's have a look at our table again – so we've suppressed the problematic cells as before. But here we have the column totals included. Does this make a difference? • Yes! This is problematic - We can see that low counts have been redacted. However, because the column totals are included it is possible to work out that there is a single 16-year-old widow with NHL.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> We may therefore need to suppress further cells; we can recalculate the totals to exclude the suppressed values or remove the totals from the tables completely.
Slide 53	<p>This slide gives an example of secondary disclosure which was mentioned briefly in the introduction.</p> <p><u>Consider these two tables</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Each of these tables is fine on its own. However, the 2nd table is nested within the first - and this can be problematic because of secondary disclosure or differencing. E.G the left-hand table shows 245 respondents in the 30-34 age group, while the subset of non-diabetics have 243 - therefore there are just 2 women with gestational diabetes in this age group. The left-hand table shows 55 respondents in the 45+ age group, while the subset of non-diabetics have 54 - therefore there are just 1 diabetics in this age group This is the biggest problem in SDC and it has no solution. If you produce a table, it's impossible to prove that no other table has been, or will be, produced that could breach confidentiality through disclosure by differencing. Therefore, all we can do is be aware of the problem and try to avoid making it likely.
Slide 54	<p>Module 5.2 Title page</p> <p>This section focuses on group disclosure and dominance.</p>
Slide 55	<p>Group disclosure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Very high percentage of a row or column total - normally it would be considered problematic if a cell accounted for close to 100% of a row total (90% and up). This is also true if a cell accounts for a very low percentage, it can be inferred that a majority of observations did not report values for the variable. In this example, a very high percentage of pupils had tried so called legal highs (considered to be a growing problem due to the dangerous effect of some of them). If we had this presented as a table, with a column for pupils having taken legal highs, and another indicating the pupils who had not, the cell for pupils having taken legal highs is close to 100%. If a parent of one of the students saw this figure, they may conclude that their child had taken legal highs, because the percentage of those who have is so high. This would then be attributing behaviour to a student for whom it may not be true, or who may not even have been surveyed. Especially when dealing with sensitive variables, we would not want statistics to result in such assumptions being made.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It's also important to remember that in social surveys the respondents are given assurances that their data will be kept confidential and it's important that we don't break those pledges.
Slide 56	<p>In this example the information is presented as percentages.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The table shows survival times following stroke by income quintile (I being the highest quintile, V being the lowest). The first issue with this output is that the researcher has not provided the counts for each cell which would be required. It would not be a good practice to expect output checkers to calculate the actual values. Go to the next slide to show the counts.
Slide 57	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This shows the underlying counts for the previous table. None of the cells has a value below the threshold as such, but there is a 0 for 5 years for income quintile V. Is this a problem? Yes. From this table we could infer that someone who is categorised as income quintile V is unlikely to survive more than 5 years. So, we have learned something potentially sensitive about a whole group of people that is potentially. In addition, it may not also be true for everyone, so we might be misattributing this characteristic to someone.
Slide 58	<p>Are there any issues here?</p> <p>Yes, again we haven't been provided with the counts and we have some 0% cells that we need to consider.</p>
Slide 59	<p>Now we have the counts, do we have a problem here?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If we look at the context in this case probably not. We would not expect accountants and office administrators to come into contact with heavy machinery, so it is logical that this is 0. So, we haven't learned anything about these professions that could be sensitive. We would refer to these as logical zeroes or structural zeros.
Slide 60	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Different data access services will have different thresholds for determining dominance. This slide should be amended accordingly. n would normally be between 40-50%. Good to emphasise here that dominance is actually rare due to the large sample sizes of most datasets.
Slide 61	<p>Dominance can be tricky to spot but is most easily seen in graphical outputs such as this time series graph:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Here we can see a chart showing the total turnover of a number of companies.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Although we have more than 10 companies each year, we can see a dramatic spike in income in 2015. • You see in the local newspaper that a large company moved into the town in that year – can we work out when and how much they turned over? • 2015 – the point is around 500,000 compared to around 50,000 either side of this, so they turnover around 435,000. • It could also be that the dramatic spike was caused that a number of companies arriving in the area for that year so a sudden spike like this will not always be problematic. • So, the dramatic increase might not be a breach of the dominance rule, it is indicative but not proof. • Therefore, further information would be needed to confirm if there has been a breach.
Slide 62	<p>Concentration Ratios:</p> <p>These may also highlight dominance issues.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This shows the concentration ratios for the 3 largest companies in several sectors. • If a concentration ratio is approaching 1, one observation might be accounting for the majority of the measure • We can see that for oil refiners, the 3 largest companies account for around 78% of the whole sector. This might suggest that there is a dominant company in this sector.
Slide 63	<p>Module 5.3 Title page</p> <p>This section looks at types of descriptive statistics.</p>
Slide 64	<p>Descriptive statistics might include measures of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the centre of a distribution (mean, median or modus), • the distribution shape (variance, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis), • how often a certain combination of attributes is observed (e.g., frequencies). <p>Reminder: N refers to the threshold set by your organisation.</p>
Slide 65	<p>Means</p> <p>The mean is the average of a series of values. This can be problematic if there are too few values in that series. For example:</p> <p>Average income = £33,350.</p> <p>Number of people = 2.</p> <p>It is easy for one person to work out what the income of the other person is.</p>

	<p>Medians</p> <p>The middle value if all values are ordered. This may be a single observation.</p> <p>Modes</p> <p>The most common number. Number of the observations with that value may fall below the threshold.</p>
Slide 66	<p>Minimum and maximum values are frequently problematic as they don't often meet the threshold rule</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As the maximum and minimum values are at the extremes of the distribution, there may be a single observation reporting that value. • So, we might be disclosing information about an individual. • In this example - • Age: min, mean & median are ok, but maximum is an issue – will be a rare observation in the data. • Annual income: The values for max are very specific & likely an outlier. Min looks ok, but could indicate a household where no one is in employment – this could be problematic • Number of vehicles: Again, max could be an issue – may be only a few households with 6 vehicles & could indicate a large household
Slide 67	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Much like maxima and minima, the values presented as quartiles, quantiles, and percentiles may refer to a single observation. • It may be necessary to demonstrate that there are sufficient observations at each value. • If the values are problematic - values could be rounded. • In the salary data for Company Y example Table 1 shows the exact salary values, as these are precise and a continuous variable, we might expect that these refer to a single observation. • In Table 2, the same values have been.
Slide 68	<p>Measures of variation and shape of distribution are normally considered to be safe statistics if they are based on sufficient observations.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If observations are low, the context can be taken into account as it might be safe to release the statistics. • software can be used to recreate the data from the variance if the bounds and mean are known. • We can avoid this by not presenting the variance for variables when the number of observations are low, or by rounding the mean or variance. • It is good practice to round these measures where possible to limit the potential risk to the data.
Slide 69	Module 5.4 Title page

	This section focuses on regression outputs
Slide 70	This slide describes what is meant by regression and ways that disclosure can occur through the publication of results.
Slide 71	<p>This slide outlines the SDC considerations for regression models.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The degrees of freedom are calculated by subtracting the number of independent variables from the number of observations used. N will be the threshold set by the secure data centre. • Sequential regressions should not differ in counts of observations of less than N: Think back to the discussion of secondary disclosure & the problem of differencing! • A full model would display the coefficients for every variable included in the regression as well as all possible interactions of those variables. • Generally safe as not good research practice to run a model on very few observations.
Slide 72	<p>Here's an example of a regression output (again not based on real data)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the issues here? • Number of observations is missing. • We also don't know what the variables included are, the variable names are likely to be meaningless to whoever is checking the output.
Slide 73	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Now we can see the number of observations and have an understanding of the variables included. • We can now properly check if there are potential problems with the models. • All ok - the number of observations is high, there aren't any issues with nesting, nor are there only categorical variables and we can calculate that the degrees of freedom are high.
Slide 74	<p>Residuals plots are a graphical representation of residuals (or errors) following the estimation of a regression model. Residuals are often plotted against a covariate.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As each residual represents a single observation, reporting residual plots should largely be avoided. • Can describe the shape of the residual rather than plot it. • Can hide the scale on the axes or use a variable that you can't observe outside the data. • Important considerations when assessing a residual plot are outliers, and what variable is used on the x-axis.
Slide 75	Module 5.5 Title page

	<p>For some data access services this section may not be necessary – for example, if your service only releases log files, then a discussion on published graphs won't be relevant, so this module could be excluded.</p>
Slide 76	<p>SDC for Graphs uses the same principles as for statistical tables.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The underlying frequencies and total counts, clear labels, and details about the data subjects are all required. • Potential issues: low counts in the tails of histograms, displaying individual observations, or min and max values.
Slide 77	<p>Histograms display the frequency distribution of a variable.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Main problem is low counts in the tails, including the maximum and minimum values. • Here we can see very few observations with a value below 10, or above 40. This could be problematic. • Also not clearly labelled so difficult to accurately assess the graph.
Slide 78	<p>Scatterplots could be problematic as often it will be individual data points that are displayed.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In this example, we can clearly see individual observations. We can see that there is a 10-year-old who smokes 4 cigarettes a day. • Grouping observations into clusters or other transformations can make scatterplots safer.
Slide 79	<p>Whilst scatterplots are often problematic, there are ways of making the plot safer through transforming the data in some way.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Here the data points are now showing each data point as a deviation from the mean rather than the actual value. • Notice that the trend line hasn't changed significantly. • The means were calculated for male and female so even if the means were published, because we do not know the gender of the observations on the graph, we would not be able to work back to identify anyone.
Slide 80	<p>Box plots are graphic representations of how data are distributed (sometimes called a 'box and whisker' plot).</p> <p>They can be problematic for a several reasons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maxima, minima, and outliers are shown and may be an SDC risk because they may represent a single or small number of observations. • This may also be true for the median. • In this example, we can see that there are outliers who survived between 10 and 13 years. • The values of these outliers could be easily calculated

Slide 81	<p>Point Maps.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each point or marker may show the location of an event or an individual or business. • In this case, the threshold is not met. • Context is important. Points showing the locations of hospitals might be less problematic than if they represented fatal car accidents. • Other types of maps may be better.
Slide 82	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heatmaps show information for regions rather than individuals. • In this example we can see the case rates for COVID 19 for a number of local authorities, but we cannot see the precise location of anyone who has tested positive. • Each region should however meet the threshold number of observations.
Slide 83	<p>Correlation's coefficients show the linear relationship between two variables.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generally safe as long as they have sufficient observations, and do not equal exactly 1 or -1. • Test statistics such as t-test, R2, F-test are generally also safe.
Slide 84	<p>A Kaplan-Meier curve is a graph showing survival curves.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Here we can see the differences in the survival between breast cancer and ovarian cancer patients. Each step change downwards indicates the number of patients who have died. • Problematic if the number of observations at a step doesn't meet the threshold.
Slide 85	<p>GROUP EXERCISE:</p> <p>This is your opportunity to consolidate the new information about the potential disclosure risks of different types of output. Divide the group into smaller groups and give them some examples of typical outputs that you see in your secure data facility.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allocate 1-2 examples to each group and then allow them 10 mins to discuss the examples. Ask them to consider: • whether the outputs have all the information required to assess them properly. • whether they would release the output & why. • If they wouldn't release the output, what would they suggest to the researcher to make it safe to release? <p>The aim of this exercise is:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To consolidate the messages in these sections and ensure they had understood the concepts. 2. To demonstrate the thought processes that output checkers go through when reviewing outputs, to demonstrate that it takes time and knowledge and that it's not

	<p>always a simple decision. This helps set expectations for researchers when waiting for outputs to be assessed.</p>
Slide 86	<p>Module 5.6</p> <p>This section is a final summary for the statistical disclosure section.</p>
Slide 87	<p>This slide is a chance to reiterate that SDC is consistent with good research output</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In general, the sorts of things that produce good research output also act as a defence against disclosure risk. • The exception to this is in class disclosure and ranking, where being able to say something about a whole group of data subjects might be valuable but also problematic.
Slide 88	<p>This slide gives some guidelines for researchers to bear in mind when putting together their outputs.</p> <p>With this simple checklist, they will increase the likelihood that their output will pass your SDC checks first time, meaning that they get their output released more quickly - something that all researchers want!</p>
Slide 89	<p>The final module is an optional extra module – its purpose is not to add to the content on data access, or statistical disclosure control.</p> <p>Its purpose is to provide additional service specific information. Experience has shown that it can be useful for both researchers and data access service staff alike to ensure at an early stage that researchers know what is expected from them before they get started on their research.</p> <p>In particular, if they know what the data access service expects to see in an output, it is easier for them to produce output that meets the requirements and that can be released more quickly.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • These next slides are a short example to show you what the service specific module might include.
Slide 90	<p>This list shows some of the topic areas that experience tells us are useful. It is not an exhaustive list, and different things will be important for different services.</p> <p>The module could also be excluded without detracting from the value and content of the overall course.</p> <p>So, the decision to include it or not will depend on the needs of the individual service and the preferred mode of delivery, length of course and so on.</p>
Slide 91	<p>Slides 91 - 93 show how such a module might start for a Secure Data Centre</p>

	This slide is a fairly standard introduction and should outline what will be covered in the module.
Slide 92	<p>This outlines the service:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Briefly explain each pathway. • We've highlighted the differences between the different pathways which you need to be aware of, but as much as possible we're working to ensure the various processes are harmonised to make it easier for researchers to use our service. • There are also a number of projects working to open up access to secure data across national borders which is a really exciting development in the world of secure data access. • So, this is a good plan to highlight any exciting developments!
Slide 93	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A video demonstration of the secure data access facility can be helpful, especially if it is easily available for researchers to view again. It can help them know what to expect from the environment and helps to reduce the number of queries secure data access facility staff receive • For anyone interested in having a look at an example of such a video, included here is the link to the UK Data Service Secure Lab video.
Slide 94	Final wrap up slide - with contact details as appropriate for your service

2.3 Further resources

1. ESSNet A Network of Excellence in the European Statistical System in the field of statistical disclosure control: Includes guidance for carrying out statistical disclosure control ([6](#)) ([PDF](#)) [ESSNet SDC - Guidelines for the checking.pdf](#) | [Felix Ritchie - Academia.edu](#)
2. Safe Data Access Professionals: Includes a statistical disclosure handbook [SDC Handbook \(securedatagroup.org\)](#)
3. Five Safes.org: provides a list of research papers relating to SDC and secure data access [www.fivesafes.org/SDC/index.html](#)

